

1 Phylogenetic inference from an 2 incomplete fossil record: Supplementary 3 information

4 Niklas Hohmann, Utrecht University, The Netherlands. Email: N.H.Hohmann@uu.nl.

5 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1559-1838>

6 Rachel C. M. Warnock, Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany.

7 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9151-4642>

8 Emilia Jarochowska, Utrecht University, The Netherlands. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8937-9405>

9 Stratigraphic forward simulation

10 We simulate two attached carbonate platforms in Julia using CarboKitten.jl v0.5.3 (Bezanson et al.
11 2017; Hidding et al. 2025). Scenario 1 is simulated under the Miller et al. (2020) sea level curve from
12 5 Ma to the present (Supplementary Figure 1). Scenario 2 is simulated under a sinusoidal sea level
13 curve comprised of 3rd and 5th order sea level changes with periods of 2.5 and 0.1 Myr and
14 amplitudes of 20 and 2 m, respectively (Supplementary Figure 2). All other model parameters were
15 kept identical between scenarios. These scenarios produce stratigraphic architectures having many,
16 but short gaps (MSG, scenario 1) and few, but long gaps (FLG, scenario 2) (Hohmann et al. 2024).

17 The simulation box is 34.5 km (dip, perpendicular to shore) by 4.5 km (strike, parallel to shore),
18 subdivided into quadratic grid cells of 150 m. Duration of the simulation was 5 Myr, with timesteps of
19 100 years. We record data every 1000 years (model resolution) as analysis below this timescale is not

20 meaningful due to limits on depositional resolution introduced by time-averaging (Kidwell et al.
21 2005; Kowalewski and Bambach 2008).

22 Subsidence rate is 20 m/Myr, roughly corresponding to the values observed in the Bahamas over the
23 Pleistocene (Hearty and Backstrom 2021). We assume insolation values of 400 W/m^2 , averaged
24 over the model time steps. Cementation is specified by the cementation time parameter (set to 1
25 kyr), which determines the half-life after which sediment is consolidated (see Hidding et al. (2025) for
26 details and discussion).

27 Carbonate platform evolution is determined by three carbonate factories (euphotic, oligophotic, and
28 aphotic) that differ in their transport properties and production profiles (see Supplementary Table 1).

29 CarboKitten implements the cellular automaton model by Burgess (2013) to generate spatially and
30 stratigraphically heterogeneous carbonate strata to emulate empirically observed complexity due to
31 competition and dispersal of organisms (Drummond and Dugan 1999). In the cellular automaton
32 model, the three carbonate facies compete for space according to a set of rules specified by a
33 viability range and an activation range. We use the default values of (4, 10) for the viability range and
34 (6, 10) for the activation range. See Hidding et al. (2025) for a detailed discussion of the cellular
35 automaton model and a justification of these ranges.

36

37 *Supplementary Figure 1: Sediment profile (A), depth-dependent carbonate production for the different carbonate factories*

38 *(B), Wheeler (chronostratigraphic) diagram (C) and eustatic sea level curve (D) for the simulation under the Miller et al.*

39 *(2020) sea level curve (scenario 1). Dashed lines indicate coeval deposition every 1 Myr, the solid line represents the*

40 *sampling location at 3 km from shore where the age-depth model was extracted (Figure 2 in main text). White lines in the*

41 *sediment profile indicate erosional surfaces, white areas in the Wheeler diagram represent gaps due to nondeposition and*

42 *erosion.*

43

44 *Supplementary Figure 2: Sediment profile (A), depth-dependent carbonate production for the different carbonate factories*
 45 *(B), Wheeler (chronostratigraphic) diagram (C) and eustatic sea level curve (D) for the simulation under the sinusoidal sea*
 46 *level curve (scenario 2). Dashed lines indicate coeval deposition every Myr, the solid line represents the sampling location at*
 47 *3 km from shore where the age-depth model was extracted (Figure 2 in main text). White lines in the sediment profile*
 48 *indicate erosional surfaces, white areas in the Wheeler diagram represent gaps due to nondeposition and erosion. White*
 49 *lines in the sediment profile indicate erosional surfaces, white areas in the Wheeler diagram represent gaps due to*
 50 *nondeposition and erosion.*

51

Factory	Parameter	Value [unit]
Euphotic	Maximum growth rate	500 [m/Myr]
	Extinction coefficient	0.6 [m ⁻¹]
	Saturation intensity	60 [W/m ²]
	Diffusion coefficient	50 [m/yr]
Oligophotic	Maximum growth rate	400 [m/Myr]
	Extinction coefficient	0.1 [m ⁻¹]
	Saturation intensity	60 [W/m ²]
	Diffusion coefficient	25 [m/yr]
Aphotic	Maximum growth rate	100 [m/Myr]
	Extinction coefficient	0.005 [m ⁻¹]
	Saturation intensity	60 [W/m ²]
	Diffusion coefficient	12.5 [m/yr]

52 *Supplementary Table 1: Model parameters specifying the carbonate factories. The production profile follows the*
53 *parametrization of Bosscher and Schlager (1992), see Supplementary Figures 1 B and 2 B for the carbonate production*
54 *profile.*

Statistic	Gap duration [Myr]					Completeness [%]
	1 st Quartile	Median	3 rd Quartile	IQR	Maximum	
Scenario 1 (MSG)	0.007	0.0220	0.039	0.032	0.279	41.02
Scenario 2 (FLG)	0.002	0.049	0.054	0.052	1.563	27.24

55 *Supplementary Table 2: Gap statistics and stratigraphic completeness at the sampling location in the two scenarios. Gap*
56 *statistics are rounded to 1 kyr (model resolution).*

57 Simulation and inference setup

58 Simulation and inference setup is described in the main text, Methods section. Code and detailed

59 instructions for reproduction are available in (Hohmann and Jarochowska 2026).

Parameter	Value [unit]
Origin	5 [Myr]
Extinction rate	0.6 [Myr ⁻¹]
Speciation rate	0.8 [Myr ⁻¹]
Sampling in the present (ρ)	1
Morphological clock rate	0.05 [Myr ⁻¹]
Molecular clock rate	0.005 [Myr ⁻¹]
Preserved fossils	30
Transition/transversion ratio kappa	5
Gamma shape parameter	0.25
Gamma rate categories	5
Stationary base frequencies	All equal

60 *Supplementary Table 3: Model parameters for the simulation setup.*

Inference setup	cFBD	sFBDw	sFBDs
Parameter			
Origin time	Exp($\lambda = 1$, offset = 5)	Exp($\lambda = 1$, offset = 5)	Exp($\lambda = 1$, offset = 5)
Extinction rate	Exp($\lambda = 1.7$)	Exp($\lambda = 1.7$)	Exp($\lambda = 1.7$)
Speciation rate	Exp($\lambda = 1.25$)	Exp($\lambda = 1.25$)	Exp($\lambda = 1.25$)
Morphological clock rate	Exp($\lambda = 20$)	Exp($\lambda = 20$)	Exp($\lambda = 20$)

Molecular clock rate	Exp($\lambda = 200$)	Exp($\lambda = 200$)	Exp($\lambda = 200$)
Transition/transversion ratio (κ)	Exp($\lambda = 0.2$)	Exp($\lambda = 0.2$)	Exp($\lambda = 0.2$)
Gamma shape parameter	Exp($\lambda = 4$)	Exp($\lambda = 4$)	Exp($\lambda = 4$)
Stationary base frequencies	Dirichlet(1,1,1,1)	Dirichlet(1,1,1,1)	Dirichlet(1,1,1,1)
Fossil sampling rate	Exp($\lambda = 0.125$)	NA	NA
Fossil sampling rate in skyline	NA	(Exp($\lambda = 0.25$), Exp($\lambda = 0.25$), Exp($\lambda = 0.25$), Exp($\lambda = 0.25$), Exp($\lambda = 0.25$))	(Exp($\lambda = 0.2$), 0.00001, Exp($\lambda = 0.2$), 0.00001, Exp($\lambda = 0.2$))

61 *Supplementary Table 4: Priors used in the inference setups. Exp is the exponential distribution parametrized by rate λ ,
62 i.e. mean = $1/\lambda$, Dirichlet() is the Dirichlet distribution with specified parameters.*

63 Convergence assessment

64 Convergence criteria are described in the Discussion section of the main text. Trace files are available
65 under <https://doi.org/10.24416/UU01-6ON0QY> (Hohmann 2026), code for automated convergence
66 assessment is available under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20826148> (Hohmann and
67 Jarochowska 2026).

68

69 *Supplementary Figure 3: Number of converged runs for the four examined combinations of inference setup (cFBD, sFBDs,*

70 *sFBDs) and fossil record structure (CFS, MSG, and FLG) as a function of the number of morphological characters. See*

71 *Methods section in main text for details on the abbreviations and convergence criteria. A small horizontal jitter was added*

72 *to the points for better visual separation.*

73

74 *Supplementary Figure 4: 90% credible interval coverage of main simulation parameters for the explored combination of*
 75 *inference setup (cFBD, sFBDw, and sFBDs) and fossil record structure (CFS, MSG, and FLG) in dependency of the number of*
 76 *morphological characters. See Methods section for details on the abbreviations and definition of the coverage. A small*
 77 *horizontal jitter was added for better visual separation.*

78 Accuracy and precision of estimates

79

80 *Supplementary Figure 5: Accuracy (relative error) vs. precision (relative 90 % CI width) of the speciation rate in dependence*

81 *of inference setup and fossil record structure. Runs where the 90 % CI covers the true parameter value are triangles, non-*

82 *covered runs are dots.*

A 30 Morph. Char.

B 100 Morph. Char.

C 300 Morph. Char.

D 1000 Morph. Char.

Case ● cFBD + CFS ● cFBD + MSG ● cFBD + FLG ● sFBDw + FLG ● sFBDs + FLG

83

84 *Supplementary Figure 6: Accuracy (relative error) vs. precision (relative 90 % CI width) of the extinction rate in dependence*

85 *of inference setup and fossil record structure. Runs where the 90 % CI covers the true parameter are triangles, non-covered*

86 *runs are dots.*

87

88 *Supplementary Figure 7: Accuracy (relative error) vs. precision (relative 90 % CI width) of the morphological clock rate in*

89 *dependence of inference setup and fossil record structure. Runs where the 90 % CI covers the true parameter value are*

90 *triangles, non-covered runs are dots.*

91

92 *Supplementary Figure 8: Accuracy (relative error) vs. precision (relative 90 % CI width) of the molecular clock rate in*
 93 *dependence of inference setup and fossil record structure. Runs where the 90 % CI covers the true parameter value are*
 94 *triangles, non-covered runs are dots.*

95 Code and data availability

96 All code is available under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20826148> (Hohmann and Jarochowska
 97 2026), simulation and inference data is archived under <https://doi.org/10.24416/UU01-6ON0QY>
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